

Figure S1. The immunofluorescence staining of type I collagen and osteocalcin (green colour) in ADSCs and bmMSCs on glass, on pure DLC, and on DLC doped with Ti (0.4, 2.1, 3.7, 6.6, 12.8 at.% of Ti) on day 7. Cell nuclei are counterstained with Hoechst 33258 (blue). Representative images were selected. Olympus IX71 microscope, IX71 digital camera, objective magnification $\times 20$, scale bar 100 μm .

Table S1. XPS take-off angle 0° to the perpendicular of the sample surface.

Sample	Atomic concentration [at.%]								
	C	O	N	Ti	Na	Ca	Si	Sn	Mg
Glass	30.95	43.22	-	-	2.66	1.46	18.54	0.26	2.90
DLC_pure	94.13	4.69	1.18	-	-	-	-	-	-
DLC_0.4Ti	93.45	4.68	0.97	0.89	-	-	-	-	-
DLC_2.1Ti	90.42	6.15	1.59	1.84	-	-	-	-	-
DLC_3.7Ti	91.00	5.85	0.31	2.85	-	-	-	-	-
DLC_6.6Ti	82.67	9.71	1.19	6.43	-	-	-	-	-
DLC_12.8Ti	68.41	21.46	0.68	9.45	-	-	-	-	-

Table S2. XPS take-off angle 81° to the perpendicular of the sample surface.

Sample	Atomic concentration [at.%]								
	C	O	N	Ti	Na	Ca	Si	Sn	Mg
Glass	41.28	45.47	-	-	1.03	0.85	9.48	0.11	1.78
DLC_pure	84.47	10.70	4.83	-	-	-	-	-	-
DLC_0.4Ti	89.29	8.92	1.79	-	-	-	-	-	-
DLC_2.1Ti	85.96	12.03	1.18	0.83	-	-	-	-	-
DLC_3.7Ti	87.28	9.57	1.63	1.52	-	-	-	-	-
DLC_6.6Ti	84.92	6.38	6.16	2.54	-	-	-	-	-
DLC_12.8Ti	86.90	9.40	-	3.71	-	-	-	-	-

Table S3. Detailed EDS analysis.

Sample	Weight percentage [wt.%]								
	C	O	Ti	Na	Mg	Al	Si	K	Ca
Glass	3.90	28.12		9.68	3.00	0.46	47.42	0.39	7.04
DLC_pure	33.24	14.35		6.39	2.23	0.35	37.60	0.26	5.58
DLC_0.4Ti	30.59	14.76	0.99	6.61	2.27	0.39	38.46	0.26	5.66
DLC_2.1Ti	27.67	16.09	3.31	7.36	2.35	0.39	36.99	0.29	5.56
DLC_3.7Ti	23.13	16.01	4.69	7.67	2.39	0.55	38.70	0.34	6.52
DLC_6.6Ti	16.81	18.03	7.81	7.13	2.48	0.39	40.84	0.32	6.18
DLC_12.8Ti	14.18	14.10	16.18	6.67	2.30	0.38	39.85	0.35	5.99

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